

THE NEW ACI 440.11-22 CODE

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ABSTRACT

The American Concrete Institute has recently published code requirements for design of concrete structures reinforced with GFRP bars that conform to ASTM D7957-22. ACI Code 440.11-22 mandates minimum requirements for nonprestressed concrete construction for structures that do not require a fire-resistance rating, and can be adopted by building codes or referenced by licensed design professionals and building officials. Strength, serviceability, durability, structural analysis, development and splicing of reinforcement, and methods to evaluate strength of existing structures are covered. This paper provides an overview of ACI Code 440.11, discussing major design requirements and key limitations.

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KEYWORDS

Codes, design, design guidelines, GFRP, structural concrete.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.